

Humus-metal Complex : Spectral Studies

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Fluorescence spectra reveal that humic hmatomelanin and fulvic acids are identical groups of humic substances. Metal ions interact with fluorescence activating groups viz., NH_2 and OH (phenolic) present in various humus-fractions to produce a complex species. Infrared spectra show that binding of hydroxylated form of metal occurs through carboxylic oxygen. Moreover co-ordination of metal with organic ligand results in a structure of the type $\text{M}-\text{O}-\text{C}-\text{R}$. IR spectra also indicate $\text{M}-\text{N}$ band formation.

A better understanding of organo-metallic interaction in soil is one of the key problems in soil science to-day. The use of infrared spectroscopy was described by various workers¹⁻⁵ to obtain information about the various atomic groupings and functional groups in soil humus. The use of I.R. spectroscopy also reveal the interaction with metal ions and has been adopted in the present study. Various fractions of humic acids exhibit visible fluorescence⁶⁻⁹. During fluorescent studies of humic acids Dutta⁸ showed that all these fractions exhibit fluorescence with emission maxima appearing at or near to 475 nm. The present work aims at obtaining molecular absorption spectra in terms of fluorescence excitation spectra and to investigate fluorescence property as a possible means of characterising humic, hmatomelanin, fulvic acids and their complexes.

Materials and Methods

Humic acid was extracted from alluvial soil (0-15cm) of West Bengal (Chinsurah Banana Plantation Centre). Crude humic acid was extracted using 0.2N Na_2CO_3 solution and separated from hmatomelanin acid by the usual procedure as discussed earlier¹⁰. Fulvic acid was separated as Ba salt by treating the centrifugate after humic acid recovery with BaCl_2 solution at pH 8 by adding dilute NaOH solution. Ba-fulvate, humic and hmatomelanin acid were dialysed and finally electrolysed. These electro-dialysed materials were treated with cation exchange resin (Amberlite IR-120 in the H-form) for 12 hr and passed repeatedly through the same resin columns until freed from traces of metallic ions. The resin treated samples were shaken with requisite amount of NaOH (calculated from b.e.c. of these preparations) dialysed against distilled water. Thus Na-form of the acids were prepared. The electro-dialysed H. A., Hy. A., and F. A. in H-form was shaken with excess of NiSO_4 , CuSO_4 (as calculated from b.e.c. of these samples) for 4 hr kept overnight and finally centrifuged. The centrifugate was shaken for 2 hr with 0.1 N NaCl solution, centrifuged and dialysed. Cu and Ni complexes of H. A., Hy. A., F. A., were thus prepared. Fluorescence measurement was done in a Farrad Spectrofluorometer. The emitting radiation as suggested by other workers^{6,9} was fixed at 520 nm. The samples were taken in a fused

quartz cell of 1 cm. thickness. The fluorescence excitation was recorded in terms of microammeter reading. The fluorescence spectra of sodium salt of H. A., Hy. A., and F. A. were recorded as also the Ni, Cu, complexes. Infra red spectra of solid samples were measured on a recording Elmer Model 521 infra red spectrophotometer (double beam) in KBr disc. It is assumed that I.R. spectra of solid samples will not be different from those in sol dispersed state.

Results and Discussion

Fluorescence excitation spectra : H. A., Hy. A. and F. A. are weakly fluorescent and require the large slit (1 m.m.). It has been observed that in addition to Rayleigh scattering there exists to smaller extent a form of scattering at 450 nm, called Raman scattering. The Raman effect has been found to be independent of the frequency of incident light. All solutions are kept sufficiently dilute so that Lambert-Beer's Law may obey. The fluorescence excitation spectra which are recorded in terms of microammeter reading, have however, been drawn in terms of excitation of radiation taking it equivalent to microammeter reading.

H. A., Hy. A., and F. A., from Chinsurah soil exhibit fluorescence with excitation maxima shown in Fig. (1,2) and Table 1. The fluorescence excitation spectra of all these fractions are more or less identical in shape. These observations led to a conclusion that H. A., Hy. A. and F. A. are identical groups of humic substances, representing some intermediate stages of a polymer series⁶. The difference in the intensity of observed fluorescence may be due to the concentration variation in fluorescing groups present in these substances. Although the exact nature of fluorescing groups could not be identified in the present investigations, the fluorescence property itself suggests the presence of either a) an aromatic nucleus substituted by at least one electron donating group, b) a conjugated unsaturated system capable of high degree of resonance, in different humic acid fractions. The former view is supported by the isolation of a number of aromatic compounds¹¹ from the oxidation degradation products of H. A., on the other hand presence of free radicals in H. A., supports the conjugated structure^{12,13}. According to Rex¹⁴ humic

Fig. 1.
 A—Na humate
 B—Na humatomelanate
 C—High Ni-Hy. A. complex
 D—Low Cu-Hy. A. "
 E—Low Ni-Hy. A. "
 F—High Cu-Hy. A. "

Fig. 2.
 ○—Ni-F.A. complex
 △—Cu-F.A. "
 ●—Na Fulvate
 ⊙—Ni-H.A. complex
 □—Cu-H.A. "

acids are large sized organic free radicals, but Stulink and Tollin¹⁵, Kononova¹⁶ are of the opinion that two stable free radicals—one a semiquinone catechol-resorcinol type copolymer and the other an electron transfer complex of quinhydrone type co-exist in humic acids.

TABLE I

Sample	Wave length in nm showing fluorescent excitation maxima
Na-humate	489
Ni-humate	475
Cu-humate	475
Na-humatomelanate	434
Ni-humatomelanate	420,550
Cu-humatomelanate	420,550
Na-fulvate	500
Ni-fulvate	487
Cu-fulvate	450

The fluorescence yield of different humus fraction-metal complexes are lower than those of humus fractions alone in all wave-lengths. Several factors viz. orientation of functional groups, flexible nature of the molecules, molecular crowding and absorption of a part of omitted radiation by the absorbing centres in them are supposed to be responsible for this¹⁷. The decrease in fluorescence yield during interaction of soil organic matter with metal ions may be due to the formation of a structure which exhibits a molecular crowding interfering with the co-planarity of the molecule or organic matter metal interaction may produce a complex species only and no chelation has occurred. Electron donating groups like-NH₂ or OH (phenolic) present in molecules containing multiple conjugated double bonds with a high degree of resonance stability (benzene nucleus in this case) may alter the degree of fluorescence. The low fluorescence yield in such organometallic complexes may be due to decrease in concentration of fluorescence groups as a result of interaction of these groups with transition metal ions to produce a stable combination in which electron donating effects of these groups are minimized. According to Weber¹⁸ colored ions viz., Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ etc, produce strong quenching effect on fluorescent substances. The fluorescent excitation may alter due to decrease in concentration of the fluorescent molecules but the fluorescent yield will remain unchanged if no newly formed species absorb exciting radiation. In case of humus substances the newly formed molecules form a part of the exciting radiation and decrease in fluorescent yield will result as some other kind of inactive light absorbing molecules have been introduced into the solution.

The fact that acid hydrolysis has no effect on fluorescent properties of humus substances,^{6,18} certainly signifies that the fluorogens responsible for fluorescence properties have not been originated from amine acid moieties of humus substances.

The fluorescent excitation maxima of humus metal combinations are shifted in general towards the shorter wavelength region. In case of Hy.A., metal complexes besides the usual peak at 420 nm, second peak is noticed in the longer wave length region (550 nm). The formation of second peak is due to polymerization effect as fluorescence peak of polyphenols is shifted to longer wavelength region in synthetic humic acids⁹.

Infra red Spectra

From the tentative assignments as given in Table 2 it is evident that infra red spectra of the soil humic acid used in this investigation are nearly identical with those reported by earlier workers^{1,2}. From the assignments of the spectrum of humic acid it may be said that it has an aromatic ring structure with hydroxyl groups in the form of polymeric association bonded with secondary amine group and hydrogen bonded H₂O molecules^{1,9}. This observation is in good agreement with that of Haworth.

TABLE 2—INFRA RED SPECTRA OF HUMIC ACID AND ITS CU-COMPLEXES

Humic acid (H.A.).	Frequency in cm ⁻¹ of		Tentative assignments
	Humic acid-low Cu complex	Humic acid-high Cu complex	
3425 (Sp,St)	3425 (Sp,St)	3300 (b,St)	Due to presence of NH ₂ OH or hydrogen bonded H ₂ O.
2900 (Sp,St)	---	---	Due to combination of OH & CO stretching of COOH group.
1650 (b,St)	1625 (m,St)	1640 (W,St)	Due to antisymmetrical stretching of free Carboxylate ion.
1380 (Sp,St)	1400 (Sp,W)	1400 (Sp,W)	Due to symmetrical stretching of free Carboxylate ion.
1000-600 (b,W)	1000-600 (b,W)	1000-600 (b,W)	Due to NH ₂ stretching & M-N bond formation.

On comparison of results of humic acid and its corresponding high and low Cu complexes, the following points are noticeable :

a) existence of the peak at 3425 cm⁻¹ in humic acid remains in almost unaltered position in its corresponding Cu⁺⁺ complexes.

b) The peak at 2900 cm⁻¹ found in humic acid completely disappears in case of Cu complexes.

c) The peak at 1650 cm⁻¹ in H. A. gradually shifted towards slightly lower frequencies in case of Cu complexes.

d) The peak at 1380 cm⁻¹ in H.A. gradually shifted towards slightly higher frequencies in case of low and high Cu complexes.

e) The peak in the broad region of 1000-600 cm⁻¹ in H.A. is uneffected in case of Cu complexes.

The observation mentioned in (a) above is due to the fact that Cu⁺⁺ forms hydroxylated type of complex³ where it exists in the form of Cu(OH)⁺. As Cu(OH)⁺ ion contributes towards the 3400 cm⁻¹ frequency the peak in this region in H.A. remains unaltered even after complexation. Besides this the form of characteristics as mentioned in (b) it may be inferred that in case of

both low and high complexes bonding of Cu occurs through carboxylic oxygen. The peaks in the regions of 1650 cm⁻¹ and 1380 cm⁻¹ in H.A. are assigned to be due to antisymmetrical and symmetrical stretching of free carboxylate ion respectively. From study of IR-spectra of known complex compounds Namamate^{1,9} has concluded that—COO stretching frequencies are affected to a great extent by co-ordination and intermolecular interaction. Therefore from the observations mentioned in (c) and (d) viz. the shifting of usual peaks at 1650 cm⁻¹ and 1350 cm⁻¹ towards slightly lower and higher frequencies, it may be concluded that co-ordination of metal with organic ligand has occurred according to the structure M—O—C—R as proposed by Nakama-

to^{2,1}. From the characteristics as stated in (e) above it is observed that a peak at a wide region of 1000-600 cm⁻¹ exist in case of H.A. and its low and high complexes. This peak in H.A. itself is probably due to NH₂ stretching bonds whereas during complex formation M-N band having frequency almost in the same region has appeared due to the NH₂ racking modes.

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